

Tunable Competition and Possible Coexistence of Magneto-Electric Phases in a Charge Ordered Manganite

M. K. Pradhan and **S. Dash***

Department of Physics and Astronomy,
National Institute of Technology, Rourkela-769008

*E_mail: dsuryanarayan@gmail.com and Mob. 9438741397

Abstract

The cross control of magnetization (electric polarization) by an external electric (magnetic) field and coupling between them in single phase material yields a new and exciting fields (1). To enhance the magneto-electric (ME) signal, effective control of a phase competition has recently been revealed as a promising approach. Herein, we report the magnetic field (H) control of the distinct ME phases in a charge ordered magnet $\text{Pr}_{0.75}\text{Na}_{0.25}\text{MnO}_3$, in which an antiferromagnetic (AFM) phase is competing with a ferromagnetic (FM) phase(2,3). The H dependent dielectric behavior is highly correlated but in contrast to their resistivity (2). The variation of ϵ with H is intrinsically associated with the coexisting phases of contrasting order. However, the ground state is FM. Using suitable experimental protocol the magnetic phases as well as electronic phases can be tuned effectively at low-H vis-à-vis to enhance the ME signal. The apparent change in ME signal in accordance with macroscopic phase competition are modelled through Maxwell's dynamical theory (4, 5).

Keywords: Charge ordering, Manganite, Competing phase, Magnetoelectric

References

1. E Dagotto, Nanoscale Phase Separation and Colossal Magnetoresistance (Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2003), and references therein.
2. S Dash et al, J. Appl. Phys. **113**, (2013) 17D912.
3. Takuya Satoh et al, Phys. Rev. B **65** (2002) 125103.
4. Cohen et al, Phys. Rev. B **8**, (1973) 8.
5. L. D. Landau, 1960. Electrodynamics of Continuous Media, 2nd ed. (Pergamon Press, 1960), pp. 42–44.